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ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-0071-6809><http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19512579>**Liquid or Precarious: a Methodological Consideration on Instance of Migrants**

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Reflecting on the current state of affairs, Zygmunt Bauman characterizes it as «... the current stage of our current modern, deregulated and disorganized, atomized and individualized, fragmented, disjointed and privatized consumer society». (Bauman & Donskis, 2016, p. viii). The key property of this stage, which includes and explains all the others, is precisely liquidity as the structure of its time and space, society and culture, values and interests, identities and communities (or, as Bauman himself would say, networks), production and reproduction. In liquid or «light» modernity, the static nature and predictability of the previous «heavy» fordist state gives way to mobility, flexibility and inconstancy of new matrices of perception and action, forms of experience and habits of consciousness. The geographical or, more broadly speaking, spatial context of life in modern society plays an ever smaller role to the point that it is completely leveled by the availability and speed of movement of people, goods, ideas, signs. «Freed from the burden of bulky equipment and numerous personnel, capital travels «lightly» without anything more than hand luggage: a briefcase, a laptop computer and a mobile phone» (Bauman, 2000, p. 58). Capital and those who follow its flows and are at the forefront of the new modernity are no longer bound to territory, and therefore freed from the tyranny of its double – the map – i.e. a clearly demarcated symbolic order. However, as is often the case, the reverse side of the freedom and flexibility of some is the rigidity and reduction of the freedom of others. On the one hand, the mobility and constant movement of capital requires the transparency of borders, the availability and reversibility of labor in connection with the «economic expediency» of a particular moment and place. To ensure this, new forms of employment are being introduced in the countries of the global north, labor laws are being deregulated, and previous social guarantees are being abolished (for the countries of the global south, these methods are nothing new).

On the other hand, the world created for cosmopolitan and mobile «tourists» is becoming an uncomfortable and hostile environment for the rest (Bauman, 1998). The meanings and values that previously determined the organization of local communities and their physical and social space are now subject to the logic of global competition and are «consumed» and thereby destroyed – whether as a result of their «economic development» or destruction due to wars, poverty and desolation. It is no more welcoming for those who were forced to leave their homes and unwittingly join this Brownian motion: «... demands to break down the last

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remaining barriers to the free movement of money flows or flows of goods that bring money are accompanied by demands to build new walls...» (Bauman, 1998, p. 93).

The logic of the community is replaced by the logic of the network, in which a new type of dominance arises. Power of this type consists in the ability to manage «liquidity», the rhythm and density of its flows, and to determine how quickly one can move along them. Factories of immobility, as Bauman calls them, act as instruments of this power. Prisons, the terminal way of limiting «liquidity», in the late modern era cannot be reduced to disciplinary institutions that manage the organization and addition of utility, in other words, the production of labor power (Foucault, 1977). In the postmodern era, the correctionalism and retributivism give way to the concept of control and isolation (Garland, 2002). As a result of ghettoization, the dualization of the city and the marginalization of the outskirts, local communities are attached to a place and alienated from urban space at the same time. The local «place» dissolves, leaving behind only a «space» cleared for precise management and surveillance (Wacquant, 2007). The erosion of space is presumably contrary to the trend of liquid mobility and the removal of the spatial dimension of the social. However, it seems to be only the other side of the present condition, which is characterized by various regimes of managing «liquidity» and the corresponding technologies of power. The ways in which the liquid of modernity spills over the surface of the social – absorbed into its texture, seeping in, filling gaps and voids, spreading out as a thin invisible membrane – are different manifestations of these technologies by which the mobile substrate of power relations is constituted. By engaging in the archaeology of these technologies, instead of taking a static snapshot of a constantly flowing society, we could reconstruct the ways and mechanisms by which it unfolds in the world.

A special way of managing «liquidity» is the refugee regime. Refugees are subject to territorial attachment and alienation, because refugee status usually implies the imposition of restrictions, such as obstacles to legal employment, a ban on leaving the country, denial of social and political rights, etc. A special case in the context of forced migrants are Ukrainian refugees in Europe, who benefit from the mechanism of temporary protection. Thus, they have all civil rights except political ones, are not restricted in crossing borders and receive various support, which depends on the host country. At the same time, this mechanism is a temporary measure and may not be extended in 2026. A distinctive feature of the situation of Ukrainian refugees in Europe is precarity, i.e. the insecurity and lack of guarantee of the conditions of their stay and activities. The concept of precarity is usually associated with the sphere of labor – contingent employment, informal employment practices, irregular work, etc. (Choonara et al. 2022). However, precarity can be seen in a broader sense as the precariousness of the conditions and means of existence, the lack of security and confidence in the future. Ontological, or as Judith Butler calls it, existential precarity is on the one hand the original state of the subject in the face of death and the finitude of life, but at the same time the distribution and recognition of precarity is a moral and political issue (Butler, 2009). As one of the opponents of this approach said, «Until a cure is discovered for the human condition, this, it seems to me, sets the bar for precarity unacceptably

low» (Choonara, 2020, p. 433). An alternative interpretation is that, as Pierre Bourdieu noted, precarity is now everywhere (Bourdieu, 1998). It penetrates not only previously untouched spheres of employment and labor, but becomes the *modus operandi* for other social fields in the era of «liquidity». What was previously defined through the dysfunction of the system – the impossibility of long-term planning – has now become one of the prerequisites for its reproduction. On the other hand, in the conditions of instability of the very basis of social interaction, social ties become interchangeable, individual subjects do not consider them as permanent, and the hypothetical temporariness of ties tends to turn into a self-fulfilling prophecy. Thus, on the one hand, we can consider the «liquid» conditions associated with risks to the livelihood and security of refugees, which we will call objectified precarity. On the other hand, there is an attitude towards temporariness, a feeling of distance and alienation internalized in new conditions, i.e. incorporated precarity. These two dimensions reinforce and complement each other, forming a special habitus of the refugee. Considering the problem in this way, we assume the need to study both aspects of precarity in their dynamic development. A parallel description of the objectified and incorporated («ontological») dimensions of precarity will allow us to interrogate the mechanisms of (re)production of precarity at the level of practices and practical attitudes and matrices of perception.

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